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Isothermal fatigue behavior of metal/CF hybrid composites with potential for intrinsic structural health monitoring

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MOTIVATION

Metal/carbon-fiber hybrid composites (MCFRPs)

WHY COMBINE METALLIC AND CARBON FIBERS

- The rigidity of CF together with the ductility and electrical conductivity of metals
- MCFRPs can intrinsically realize aircraft functions such as impact tolerance, signal transport, lightning-strike protection

METASTABLE AUSTENITIC STAINLESS STEEL FIBERS

- More ductility and damage tolerance in the composite
- Additional functionality through improved electrical conductivity
- Possibility of non-destructive structural health monitoring (SHM) through the austenite-martensite phase transformation
- Characterization of isothermal fatigue behavior necessary to validate SHM method at aviation standard testing temperatures

PROJECT OBJECTIVE

Isothermal fatigue characterization of CFRP and MCFRP

FOLLOW-UP TO A PREVIOUS PROJECT

- Optimal MCFRP laminate layup determined
- Multi-directional layup with stainless steel fibers on the periphery

ISOTHERMAL FATIGUE CHARACTERIZATION

- In the LCF and HCF regimes, up to 2×10^6 loading cycles at RT, -55°C and $+120^\circ\text{C}$ with $R = 0.1$
- Constant and increasing load-amplitude tests (CLA & ILA)
- Microscopy and crack propagation analysis
- Simultaneous monitoring of
 - Surface temperature
 - Electrical resistance
 - Magnetic response due to deformation-induced martensitic phase transformation

Backe et al., 2018 [1]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Laminate fabrication and sample preparation

FABRICATION AT TU KAISERSLAUTERN

- Autoclave process to fabricate CFRP and MCFRP plates
 - Diameters: 7 μm carbon fiber bundles, 70 μm steel fibers
- Samples cut from plates using water-jet cutting

TESTING SETUP

- Zwick/Roell HC-25 servo-hydraulic testing machine ($F_{\text{max}} = 25 \text{ kN}$), equipped with:
 - (1) pressurized sample clamps, (2) force sensor, (3) strain gauge, (4) thermocouples, (5) 4-point resistance measurement
- Ferritscope to measure martensite content of steel fibers in MCFRP

FATIGUE TESTING PARAMETERS

- $R = 0.1$
- Up to 2×10^6 cycles
- $f = 5 \text{ Hz}$ (RT and $120 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), $f = 10 \text{ Hz}$ @ $-55 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Laminate Layup

CFRP

MCFRP

Khatri et al., 2022 [2]

CFRP

- Multidirectional layup with two 0° peripheral layers, forming a total of four 0° CF layers
- 60 vol. % CF in epoxy resin

MCFRP

- Eight SF layers replacing the outermost 0° and 90° CF-ply, resulting in two 0° CF-layers and four 0° SF-layers
- CF and SF content: 49 vol. % and 18 vol. % respectively

RESULTS - I

Isothermal tensile tests

- UTS of CFRP higher, due to the two additional 0° plies in its layup
- UTS generally higher at lower temperatures
- Failure strain comparable between CFRP and MCFRP for all temperatures

RESULTS - II

Increasing load amplitude tests

- $\Delta\sigma_a = 5 \text{ MPa}$ every 5×10^3 to 1×10^4 cycles per step (ΔN)

CFRP

- No stiffness degradation until $\sim 50\%$ of N_b
- ΔR constant until failure of 0° CF-layers

MCFRP

- Stiffness degradation more reactive to the increasing load
- Progressive ΔT at RT
- ΔR dependent on SF breakage

RESULTS - III

Constant load amplitude tests

CFRP

- Fatigue softening and stiffness degradation observed at all three test temperatures
- No significant change in ΔR until failure

MCFRP

- Initial fatigue softening, followed by a stable stiffness behavior
- Increase in ΔR with SF breakage

RESULTS - IV

S-N Curves and the martensitic phase transformation

- Both laminates show higher stiffness at lower temperatures
- CFRP is in general stiffer due to the difference in the number of 0°-layers in the laminate
- MCFRP Maximum martensite content of 8.5 % observed, only at -55 °C

- SHM not possible at RT and above due to fiber composition
- Even though the steel fibers lie within the tolerances of the standard, the Ni and Cr equivalent contents measured result in a stable austenite phase at RT
- A more tailored chemical composition of the steel fibers can ensure metastability at RT

RESULTS V

Microscopy and failure behavior - CFRP

Khatri et al., 2022 [2]

CFRP

- Damage in the outer layers observed as early as 13 % · N_f
- The central 0°-plies intact until after 50 % · N_f
- Delaminations and accelerated damage observed after 75 % · N_f

RESULTS V

Microscopy and failure behavior - MCFRP

Khatri et al., 2022 [2]

[2]

MCFRP

- No significant damage up to $\sim 50\% \cdot N_f$
- Steel fiber delamination and breakage precede those of CF
- Accelerated damage of the CF layers observed after $85\% \cdot N_f$

Summary

HIGHER STIFFNESS OBSERVED AT LOWER TEMPERATURES

- CFRP up to 30 %, MCFRP up to 40 % stiffer at -55 °C compared to RT

MCFRP SAMPLES EXHIBITED SLOWER FATIGUE ONSET

- Higher plastic deformation observed for MCFRP under fatigue loading
- The inclusion of steel fibers resulted in a more ductile failure behavior

ALLOY COMPOSITION OF STEEL FIBERS CRITICAL

- No martensitic transformation observed at RT
- Up to 8 % martensite measured after CLA tests at -55 °C
- Ni and Cr content in the stainless steel fibers critical, even while remaining within the limits of the DIN 1.4301 standard

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REFERENCES

- [1] Backe, S., Balle, F., Hannemann, B., Schmeer, S., Breuer, U.: Fatigue properties of multifunctional metal and carbon-fiber-reinforced polymers and intrinsic capabilities for damage monitoring, *Fatigue Fract Eng Mater Struct.*42:143–151, 2018.
- [2] Khatri, B., Rehra, J., Schmeer, S., Breuer, U., Balle, F.: Metal/Carbon-Fiber Hybrid Composites—Damage Evolution and Monitoring of Isothermal Fatigue at Low and Elevated Temperatures. *J. Compos. Sci.*, 6(3), 67, 2022.